

The South African Police Service is Currently Experiencing Ethical and Principled Leadership Crisis on a Strategic Level

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Abstract:- This research responds to a call for further research on leadership in the South African Police Service. Effective police leaders become adept at responding to challenge. Ethical leadership is a necessary ingredient for successful crisis management. Police leaders are responsible for preserving democratic, economic and professional values in their capacity as leaders, in both the short and longer term. They should be able to master and deal with daily operations, emergency events and various types of crises, incremental developments and reforms, both separately and simultaneously. This comprises a large range of situations and management tasks. Against this background, we will argue that leadership both within and by the police has become more complex and challenging in recent years. At the same time, we believe that police leadership is a crucial resource in order to ensure the efficient operation and development of the police service, and essential if the police are to function efficiently with the level of quality and ethical standards that meet the demands and expectations of a liberal democracy. Drawing a direct line between these two may be oversimplified, but there is unquestionably a connection between the leadership issues that have plagued the SAPS for many years and the agency's declining effectiveness in preventing, investigating, and prosecuting crimes and lawlessness. It goes without saying that an ineffective police force has a detrimental impact on people's freedom and security, on investment and economic progress, and on the stability of the entire nation. Unfortunately, there is little evidence that the issue is receiving the attention that it merits from the nation's political leaders.

Keywords: *Ethical Leadership, Leaders' Ethicality, Strategic Leadership, Strategic Management, Relationship Management, Leadership Continuum.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the root of all organizational issues and its social position is institutionalized and recognized (Crevani et al., 2010; Tourish, 2013). Police professionalism and sustaining police integrity are two things that are frequently cited as being most dependent on police leadership. Law enforcement officers must be moral role models. Whether there is accountable leadership or not, it will ultimately have a big impact on society. Research into

the causes and effects of ethical leadership is highly significant as a result of the increase in executive leader scandals in the police (Brown & Trevino 2006). Leaders who respect ethics can affect how their team behaves by applauding moral behavior and chastising immoral behavior based on the consequences they have on others (Brown & Trevino, 2006).

Organizational psychology leadership concepts like transformational leadership and operant leadership provide direction on how to effectively promote ethical behavior. It has been demonstrated that ideas such leader transparency, fairness, punctuality, consistency, and proportionality of answers to performance are effective, whereas unjust treatment can have a detrimental impact on job performance and rule adherence. The lack of supervisory presence, the failure of higher officers to establish uniform standards, and supervisors' willing blindness to corrupt behavior are among the shortcomings that have been identified. Recent advancements in police demonstrate a number of measures that can foster leadership responsibility across the organization, such as transparent accountability frameworks, values declarations, management intervention models, and decentralization of complaint handling. Combining these efforts and including the leadership traits stated above can provide a complementary framework for enhancing management, leadership, and ultimately integrity.

• *Framework for Conceptualizing Ethical Leadership*

The first study on the concept of ethical leadership was done by Trevino et al. (2000). Their definition is founded on a comparison of social scientific and philosophical perspectives on ethical leadership. Philosophers defined ethical leadership from a normative viewpoint based on what ethical leaders are expected to do. Ciulla (2004) emphasizes the importance of upholding and respecting the rights and humanity of others when discussing how to lead ethically. On the other hand, social science literature that combines leadership and ethics has been used to research ethical leadership. Therefore, studies have linked perceived personal qualities of leaders, such as honesty, integrity, and trustworthiness, to their efficacy (Brown and Trevino, 2006).

Effective leadership has also been combined with cognitive-based trust, which refers to demonstrating reciprocal care and worry as well as dependability and dependability. To critically examine the idea of ethical

leadership, Trevino et al. (2003) conducted an exploratory study. As a result, ethical leadership has been closely linked to personality traits like honesty, ethics, reliability, and fairness. This aspect is known as "moral person," and it represents "the leaders' personal traits, character, and altruistic motivation" (Brown and Trevino, 2006: 597). The second component of moral leadership is referred to as "moral management," and it describes the steps leaders take to influence their followers' ethical and immoral behavior. The second viewpoint on moral leadership has many different facets. In order to construct ethical leadership on a multi-dimensional basis, researchers (De Hoogh and Den Hartog, 2008, 2009; Kalshoven et al., 2010) built on the behavioral dimensions originally defined by Brown et al. (2005). This suggests that the construction of ethical leadership is founded on various behavioral dimensions. However, it is important to note that Brown et al.' construct served as the basis for the multidimensional concept's development. Ethical leaders are frequently viewed as fair and trustworthy, ethical leadership is anticipated to manifest through socioemotional foundation (Brown and Trevino, 2006). To put it another way, since moral leaders are known to treat people fairly and to be driven by altruism, followers should return the favor in a manner that benefits their leaders and organizations (Mayer et al. 2009).

➤ *Police Leadership in the South African Police Service*

Leadership behaviors are prioritized in police leadership. It is recommended that leaders demonstrate traits including dependability (Murphy and Drodge, 2004), honesty and integrity (Vito and Vito, 2015), decision-making (Andreescu and Vito, 2010), and innovation (Schafer, 2013). Desirable leadership behaviors turn into abstract, impossibly high "wish lists" that represent what "ought to be" (Rost, 1993). The "reality" of leadership for police commanders is ignored, as are the definitions and understandings of leadership Grint (2005a:34) draws a conclusion:

"The most intriguing thing about making lists is that, by the time the list is finished, the only reasonable explanation for the possessor of such a talent base is "God."

Effectiveness and "what works" in police leadership are major policy concerns. Effective leadership behaviors are crucial in the formal discourse of police leadership, according to the College of Policing Leadership Review (2015a:6). We must first define desirable qualities in an ideal police leader in order to develop a police leadership that is appropriate for its purpose in a profession that is evidence-based, ethical, and serving a diverse, democratic community. This makes police leadership effective across the board. Leadership becomes into a "commodity that, once identified, can be bottled and distributed to hungry organizations," according to Murphy and Drodge (2004:1). This method falls short in capturing the complexity of leadership, including why and for whom certain leadership behaviors are "effective" or "ineffective" and when they are. The method ignores the "myriad of contexts within which police leaders must operate," (Wright et al. 2008:66).

➤ *Leadership Failings*

South Africa's high turnover of national police commissioners is a symptom of the country's fractured police service says security analyst Ziyanda Stuurman. Since the advent of democracy, a number of prominent police officers have failed to complete a term in office, including National Police Commissioner. "I believe it speaks to the high level of politicization of that position, and what that has meant is that there is not this incredibly high rate of turnover," the author says. The issue at the top of the SAPS can be illustrated by looking at the number of senior officers that are being investigated for, or implicated of, serious crimes and irregularities, or who have actually been found guilty for these crimes. Questions about police leadership have also been raised by scandals involving prominent police commissioners listed below:

- *Commissioner, Jackie Selebi:* He was appointed national police commissioner in February 2000 to 2008. In 2010 he was sentenced to 15 years in jail for taking bribes from drug dealer Glenn Agliotti.
- *Commissioner, Bheki Cele:* Bheki Cele, who was chosen to succeed Commissioner Selebi from 2009 to 2011, served for only two years before being suspended for claims of improper spending and poor management in connection with the leasing of a building. He was finally fired in 2013, but he later returned as the minister of police in 2018.
- *Commissioner, Riah Phiyega:* She was appointed in 2012 and was suspended by then president, Jacob Zuma in October 2015, following the findings of the commission of inquiry into the Marikana tragedy. Commissioner Cele's successor, the Farlam Commission of Enquiry into the Marikana Massacre recommended that Commissioner Riah Phiyega's fitness for office be investigated despite the fact that she had never been accused of corruption. Instead, the group of "ministerial reference" found that she had lied and cheated in relation to performance and disciplinary issues.
- *Commissioner, Khomotso Phahlane:* The former acting National Commissioner was fired in July 2020 after he was found guilty of elements of dishonesty. Khomotso Phahlane was chosen to serve as Acting National Commissioner after she was suspended in 2015. However, Mr. Phahlane was expelled from the SAPS in 2020 after being accused of fraud and corruption in 2018. His trial just got underway and is still pending.
- *Commissioner, Khehla John Sitole:* was chosen in 2017, not long before the Ramaphosa and Zuma factions of the ANC engaged in a fierce power struggle at the ANC's five-early National Conference. The High Court determined that Mr. Sitole had violated his obligations when he purchased an intelligence "grabber" at a much inflated price, which grabber was then used to monitor conversations during the ANC conference. As a result, Mr. Sitole is now very likely to be fired. Khehla Sitole, the police commissioner, resigns by mutual consent and "in the best interests of the country." On March 31, 2022, National Commissioner Khehla John Sitole

resigned from his job 'by mutual accord' with President Cyril Ramaphosa.

- It doesn't get any better at the levels just beneath National Commissioner. When they appeared in court toward the end of the previous year, the Deputy National Commissioner, Bonang Mgwenya, and 14 more officers were accused of fraud, theft, corruption, and money laundering. Along with the Gauteng Provincial Commissioner and Deputy Commissioner, she is charged. (This is the same case that Mr. Phahlane, the former National Acting Commissioner, is appearing in.
- Arno Lamoer, the then provincial commissioner for the Western Cape, was sentenced to six years in prison in May 2018 for corruption, along with two other soldiers. Mmamonye Ngobeni, a former KwaZulu-Natal Provincial Commissioner, was charged in court in October 2020 with corruption and thwarting the course of justice in relation to lodging tenders from the 2010 FIFA World Cup.
- Commissioner, Richard Mdluli, who served as chief of criminal intelligence from 2009 to 2012, is another case involving top police management that has to be brought up. It is commonly acknowledged that Mr. Mdluli took advantage of his position to promote the then-president Zuma and hire several of his own relatives informally. But Mr. Mdluli's five years in prison were due to the fact that he had abducted and abused his former lover's husband.
- General Fannie Masemola is the new national police commissioner.

➤ *Lack of stability*

From Generals Fivaz to Sitole inclusive, there have been nine National Commissioners since 1995, four of whom have served in an acting capacity. This shows that the median tenure of each of them in the job was three years. Because Mr. Fivaz and Mr. Selebi each held office for 14 years, the most recent seven Commissioners actually served an average of only 20 months each.

This extraordinarily swift turnover hasn't promoted leadership stability. Within the vast SAPS organization, no one has been able to establish their authority or management style, and no one has been able to cultivate and educate a corps of second-tier leaders from which their successor could be chosen. Naturally, since they were unsure of their future status, acting commissioners were unable to settle into their roles or make long-term preparations. In the meantime, some of them have also acted hurriedly, modifying systems and installing top officials without according to protocols, giving the impression that they wished to make major institutional changes before their acting tenure was over in addition to the fact that this has no stabilizing effect.

Analyzing this lack of stability requires taking into account how unstable the rest of the state apparatus was during the state capture years. Numerous senior employees were disregarded or forced to resign from their positions due to political influence in institutions like the National Prosecuting Authority, the State Security Agency, and the

SA Revenue Service, to name a few. Even the most capable and perfect SAPS Commissioner would have had to do their duties while keeping an eye out for political ploys that may, at any point, have ended their term. Not exactly the makings of a cool, collected leader.

II. UNDERSTANDING POLICE LEADERSHIP

Position and rank in the police are only loosely correlated with the activity and resource of leadership. At all levels of police organizations, it is a resource that is required (Fleming, 2015). Leadership is used on the front lines as well as at the strategic, medium, and senior levels. Every police officer evaluates situations, makes judgments, communicates, and in doing so, demonstrates leadership in the course of their daily work. If the police organization is to be seen by both internal and external people as respectable, effective leadership is crucial. In an environment that is becoming more dynamic and complicated, effective leadership is a requirement for police organizations as well (Fleming, 2015).

In his 1955 paper "Skills of an Effective Administrator" for the Harvard Business Review, Robert L. Katz found that administrators needed three key competencies: technical, interpersonal, and conceptual. This is referred to as the "Three-Skill Approach" by Northouse (2013). According to Habersfeld (2013), who cites Swanson et al. (1998), there are three different sets of competencies or talents that can be used to understand police leadership. Similar managerial abilities to those mentioned by Katz in his 1955 article are described by Swanson et al. This strategy for police leadership, in our opinion, is quite beneficial.

The Police Leadership Qualifications Framework (PLQF), introduced by the National Police Improvement Agency (NPIA) in England and Wales, has formulated the following definition of police leadership: "the ability to effectively influence and combine individuals and resources to achieve objectives that otherwise would be impossible" (Johannessen & Glomseth, 2015: 7). Glomseth writes this in the Norwegian book on police leadership. According to Gibson and Villiers, "leading by example, leading others, leading teams, leading units, and leading organizations" are the five integrated levels that make up leadership (Gibson & Villiers, 2006: 7).

The foundation of this strategy is the identification of the knowledge and abilities required to fulfill and maintain effective leadership roles. This methodology can be used to educate and train police leaders so they can provide the police force with competent leadership both individually and collectively. "(Police) leaders are expected to generate a sense of purpose that both motivates and directs followers so that they voluntarily make a meaningful contribution to the organization," write Andreescu and Vito (2010).

Police leadership is described by Habersfeld (2006) as "the ability to make a split-second decision and take control of a potentially explosive situation that develops on the

street." She also asserts that "police leadership is the ability of each police officer, beginning from the first day on the job, to take charge of a situation on the street. This term encompasses any circumstance that necessitates the assertion of control. The level and scope of control shift as police officers advance in their careers. Police leadership is about the capacity to assume control since police work is founded on the mandate to use coercive action to gain compliance. The ideals of doing things correctly and doing the right thing will frequently collide in police leadership. Three different styles of police leadership are identified by Golding and Savage (2008):

- Command (ordering, instructing, and directing leadership).
- Leadership (leadership, interactional leadership).
- Management (management / administration).

These three categories may also be seen as skills that police commanders need to possess in order to properly carry out their duties and address a range of issues. Grint (2010: 21) emphasizes these styles of leadership by asserting that effective leadership entails posing queries and opening the door to discussion. While command-based leadership entails giving precise directions and controlling resources, administration entails organizing procedures. As a result, there are certain circumstances and issues that call for unique leadership strategies. Grint compares the various managerial styles to three types of issues: "critical," "tame" (common), and "wicked" complicated (cited in Glomseth, 2015: 149-150). According to Moggré et al. (2017), because internal and external forces are always interacting, police leadership is seen to be more particular and context-sensitive than conventional leadership.

➤ *Ethical Leadership*

Ethics in leadership are "the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision making," according to Brown, Trevino, and Harrison (2005: 120). According to Brown, et al.'s (2005) definition of ethical leadership, a leader should be both a moral individual and a moral manager, constantly supporting and upholding moral standards through their words and deeds. After conducting a thorough review of the literature, Brown and colleagues defined ethical leadership as "the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making" (Brown et al., 2005: 120). This definition implies that: 1) because their conduct is accepted as appropriate, ethical leaders serve as role models for followers. 2) Moral leaders engage with supporters to make their case, 3) Since ethical leaders aspire to behave ethically at all times, they set ethical standards and practices, encourage workers to act ethically, and penalize dishonest behavior. 4) Ethical leaders raise the ethical implications of their choices, integrate ethical considerations into the decision-making process, and, above all, strive to reach morally sound decisions.

According to the definition, ethical leadership is one of the constructive leadership philosophies that places a strong emphasis on the actions of the leader and distinguishes between these and real behavior. Ciulla asserts that a moral leader is a successful leader.

The art of ethical leadership involves motivating others and making wise choices in accordance with a predetermined set of principles, such as justice, accountability, trust, honesty, equality, and respect. These principles actually serve as the cornerstone of responsible leadership. Ethics-based leadership is guidance that has an impact on followers. In order to enhance ideals, dignity, fairness, integrity, charisma, and innovation without jeopardizing how we should act, leaders make decisions that reflect their own moral development. The primary objective of any organization's leader is to persuade the membership to pursue objectives and ultimately realize the organization's vision. Deontological leadership ethics considers a leader's actions to have intrinsic moral status, whereas teleological leadership ethics views a leader's action as lacking any intrinsic moral status. Ethical leadership is defined as that which is morally good or deemed morally right (Kanungo, 2001). In light of this, the concept of ethical leadership was developed, and it was described as "the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making" (Brown, Treviño & Harrison, 2005: 120).

Individuals who practice ethical leadership adhere to a set of values and principles that are widely accepted as providing a solid foundation for the common welfare. Integrity, regard, confidence, justice, openness, and honesty are a few of these. Since scholars have become more concerned with ethical behaviors, ethical leadership has become a distinct leadership approach (Brown et al. 2005; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008, 2009; Kanungo, 2001). Michael, and Linda (2007: 140–155), state that ethical leadership emanates from the awareness to conceive the workers, customers and all the related parties that constitute the legal, economic and social environment of the organization as the stakeholder of the management. In fact, ethical leadership becomes the requirement of both the social responsibility and the social awareness of the organization and it is not such easy to find a field in which normative principles are not dictated by the concept of ethics. In this interpretation of ethical leadership, connecting with followers is balanced with an emphasis on fairness, harmony, mutual wellbeing and a genuine concern for all stakeholders, not just those within the organization. The idea is that both leaders and their followers should act in an ethically sound way.

To advance the common welfare is the goal of moral leadership (Bass and Steidlmeier, 1998). The common good can be thought of as the greatest good for the greatest number of people, understanding that not everyone's understanding of "the good" can be satisfied but that the greatest number of people should feel that their good is

being sought in a plural society with multiple cultures and potentially divergent values. According to Velasquez, Andre, Shanks, and Meyer (1992), the conditions of social life that allow citizens access to the resources they need to realize their own aspirations are what constitute the common good. According to Velasquez, et al. (1992), putting this idea into practice means that society will create the social systems, institutions, and environments that support and sustain the common good.

A managerial approach called ethical leadership places a strong emphasis on the ethical side of leadership. It describes a leader's values, moral character, and moral conduct at work, as well as how they relate to their team members, groups, and society (Gabriunas, 2017). Ethics has always been concerned with the values that an organization considers desirable; obviously, any organization's primary objective is to achieve growth through consistent performance. It is connected to qualities like trust, integrity, thoughtfulness, charisma, and justice (Becker, and Thomas, 1998). Being a "moral person" and a "moral manager" are the two major facets that the ethical leadership concept represents (Brown and Trevino, 2006). In order to be a moral person, the leader must behave in a normatively acceptable manner. The definition of appropriate behavior is not explained by the theory of ethical leadership, but Brown et al. (2005) provide a number of instances, including being honest, fair, trustworthy, and nurturing. To be a moral manager, one must control the ethical behavior of followers by addressing ethical issues, promoting followers' ethical behavior, and reining in their immoral behavior. A growing interest among managers and academics alike is ethical leadership. Since that time, study has focused heavily on exploring workplace ethical issues. Although ethical aspects have primarily been anchored in transformational and charismatic leadership styles, Brown, Trevino, and Harrison (2000) were the first to examine the conceptual basis of ethical leadership from the viewpoint of organization members (Bass and Avolio, 2000).

Their main goal is to contribute to our knowledge of the universality of ethical leadership style and the relationships between ethical leadership and other variables in its nomological system (Brown et al., 2005). Concern over "ethics sensitivity" has grown as corporate governance has been questioned and leadership conformity has been called into question (Fulmer, 2005). Leaders frequently play a significant role in promoting morality and ethical standards in the workplace. However, some individuals might think that ethics are private and have nothing to do with management. "The reality, however, is that ethics have very little, if anything, to do with administration or leadership. Additionally, managers' behavior permeates corporations, and their behavioral expectations are a crucial component of the corporate atmosphere and, once stabilized, culture (Mihelic, 2010:31).

In conclusion, moral leadership is essential for establishing the tone and has a significant impact on both followers as individuals and an organization as a whole. When exercising ethical leadership, a person must take a

long-term perspective on the organization's viability and, in doing so, must take into account the needs and interests of the organization's constituents. The ethical leader's ultimate goal should be the advancement of the community in which the organization is located. The ethical leader also works in a national and international setting where there may be a nuanced understanding of what being ethical entails. When making choices and setting an example of ethical behavior, the astute ethical leader will need to try to comprehend these subtleties.

➤ *Principles of Ethical Leadership*

Ethical leadership is about walking the walk as much as it is about talking the talk. Ethical leaders have high expectations for their employees, and they hold themselves to the same standards. Leaders also expect other members of their team to lead by example. Practitioners and scholars of ethical leadership point to five key principles of ethical leadership:

- *Honesty*: Dishonest behavior is a form of lying or misrepresenting reality. Dishonest behavior by leadership creates an atmosphere of mistrust and can lead to leadership being seen as not dependable. People will lose faith in dishonest leadership. As a result, ethical leaders must behave with honesty.
- *Justice*: Ethical leaders are also concerned with issues of justice and fairness. These types of leaders prioritize treating everyone in an equal manner and placing justice and fairness at the center of their decision-making more broadly. They make a rule of never giving certain individuals special treatment, except when a particular situation demands it for justice.
- *Respect*: Leaders who convey respect to their peers and employers approach others with an inherent sense of their worth and value as individuals. Respect means listening carefully to others and confirming their inherent value. Leaders should also mentor others to become aware of their purpose, values and needs so that ethical qualities spread throughout the organization.
- *Community*: Ethical leaders behave with altruism. They place the welfare of their subordinates high in their esteem, and engage in activities like team building, mentoring, and empowerment behaviors. This means ethical leadership helps to build community. These leaders take into account the values and purpose of their employees as well as of the organization as a whole.
- *Integrity*: Integrity refers to the quality of having a strong moral purpose and being honest. Ethical leaders demonstrate appropriate values to those around them via their behavior. Leaders who act with integrity can strengthen the organization by attracting talented, ethical hires. People generally want to work for leaders they perceive as acting with integrity. Investors and customers feel the appeal of leadership that acts with integrity and are more likely to be attracted to those organizations.

➤ *Ethical Leadership Role*

Employers may be more likely to engage in additional beneficial organizational practices if they follow ethical leadership, which is a powerful leadership approach (Piccolo, Greenbaum, and Hartog, 2010). According to research, workers who are led by moral example value how their efforts help the company achieve its objectives (Piccolo et al., 2010). Masood and Zia-ur-Rehman (2017) contend that a corporation's performance is influenced by the way ethical leadership is practiced, especially by catering to the needs and interests of the workforce (Chen and Silverthorne, 2005; Masood and Zia-ur-Rehman, 2017). This is in line with the definition of leadership put forth by Drucker, (1974), who claimed that it is the act of inspiring and directing subordinates to achieve organizational objectives at the same time that the leader is motivating and leading employees to do the same.

The aim of leadership has evolved and grown over time to include elements of upholding high moral standards. The leadership style within a company has a significant impact on the attitudes of the workforce. Leaders must have a greater psychological impact on employees than other members of the company because they directly assign employees' tasks. The promotion of physical and psychological health at work, as well as lowering turnover plans, are all benefits of workplace well-being, according to research (Wright and Cropanzano, 2000; Wright, Cropanzano, and Bonett, 2009). One definition of ethical leadership is a leading approach that is motivated by respect for ethical principles. People-focused and aware of how their actions affect others, ethical leaders make ethical choices. Since there is a clear discrepancy between rhetoric and practice in terms of employee behavior, ethical behavior cannot be recognized simply by setting rules on ethics (Ott and Dicke, 2012: 84).

➤ *Identifying Characteristics of Ethical Leadership*

What constitutes ethical leadership must be addressed in light of recent events. According to Brown and Trevino (2006), ethical leadership requires honesty, integrity, and trustworthiness in addition to cognitive trust Brown Trevino and Harrison (2005) contend that ethical leadership entails modeling the most defensible and fitting behavior through one's own behavior, that of others, and that of one's relationships with others. They also contend that ethical leadership involves promoting this behavior to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making. Considering ethical leadership in terms of right or wrong, good or bad, should or ought, and good or evil is how Bass and Steidlmeier (1999) and Nel, Weiner, Haasbroek, Poisat, Sono, and Schultz (2008: 592) frame the topic. In a similar vein, Miheli et al. (2010) claim that ethics is the set of moral. Similar to this, Werner (2011) contends that a code of ethics is important because it enables organizational leaders to specify their organizational ethical values and provide rules for making moral decisions.

Werner (2011) adds that a code of ethics must also outline all applicable consequences and be continuously implemented through rewards for compliance and sanctions

for non-compliance. The latter claim is supported by Alshammari, Almutairi, and Thuwaini (2015), who assert that moral principles and values govern organizational behavior and direct leaders' actions in influencing followers' desired behavior in the direction of the organization's goal. Werner (2011) further contends that having an understanding of the ingredients for ethical leadership necessitates having a leader who will serve as an ethical role model for their workforce. Similar to this, Nzimakwe (2014) contends that, from the perspective of leadership, Ubuntu calls for leaders to set an example for subordinates. According to Kalshoven, Den Hartog, and De Hoogh (2010), moral leaders have a responsibility to act morally. According to Engelbrecht et al. (2016), a leader's ethical fairness, compassion, and care for their subordinates are qualities that help followers once again have faith in them. According to Bello (2012), a leader's role is to inspire followers to follow in his or her footsteps while also setting an example for the group, defining the norms and values, and living up to expectations. According to Conger and Riggio (2007), ethical leadership has two elements. The first is that leaders must act morally while performing their duties. Second, leaders influence the ethical climate of their organizations and communities. Cheteni and Shindika (2017) assert that because of their positions and authority inside their organizations, leaders serve as role models.

➤ *Fostering an Ethical Workplace Culture*

Cheteni and Shindika (2017) contend that moral leaders create a moral workplace by implementing procedures that firmly adhere to ethically sound principles. Importantly, moral leaders show their followers that morality comes before anything else, even when doing so means sacrificing the organization's short-term goals. According to Werner (2011), developing a team is a crucial strategy for growing an organization. It can be used to increase member trust, which lowers resistance and staff conflicts and eases team tension, as well as to build staff cohesion and expose any hidden agendas. When there are role models in the workplace, people will want to act like them, according to Mayer et al. (2009) and Werner (2011). Conger and Riggio (2007) go on to say that workers are impacted in a similar way when they see bad behavior punished and good behavior rewarded. It is therefore possible that the current failings can only be corrected if the leaders uphold the ethical leadership ideals.

Similar to this, Messick and Bazerman (1996) and Yukl (2010: 99) note that many CEOs nowadays encounter numerous challenging and sometimes explosive circumstances in which they must make choices that could be advantageous to their organizations or to others subordinates and stakeholders. Additionally, they advise effective executives to devise plans for acquiring a complete understanding of their surroundings if they don't already have one. The latter view is supported by the claims made by Acar, Kaya, and Sahin (2012) that the leadership process requires that work be divided evenly within the organization and that rights and obligations are assigned in an equitable manner. They further contend that in order to be effective, leaders should conform their behavior to moral standards,

some of which include justice, equality, honesty, integrity, and respect for human rights. According to Malik et al. (2016), treating employees fairly, upholding moral principles, and monitoring employees all make a significant contribution to good moral behavior and a positive attitude in the workplace. Winston (2007), on the other hand, claims that ethical leadership and decision-making in organizations have been the subject of many ethical issues, particularly in light of high-profile corporate scandals. Most importantly, Messick and Bazerman (1996) and Werner (2011) assert that organizations' ethical leadership and decision-making are heavily influenced by their accountability to a variety of stakeholders. Organizations and their stakeholders are more likely to succeed when they adhere to the aforementioned idea. (Winston, 2007). According to Malik et al. (2016), employees must follow the right instructions from their managers in order to meet the objectives and standards of the organization.

➤ *Advantages of Ethical Leaders*

Many experts and professionals have proposed numerous benefits of moral leaders. Following are a few advantages of responsible leadership in organizations:

- *Ethical Leadership can Help Employees be More Open to Change:* According to Beer and Nohria (2000), people's attitudes may be a factor in why most change initiatives don't produce the desired outcomes (Eby, Adams, and Russell, 2000). Because it may be a crucial factor in ensuring effective execution of change, readiness to change is necessary for successful change (Vakola, 2014). Organizations only adapt and respond through their members, according to George and Jones (2001: 420). In order to effectively implement changes in organizations, individual readiness to change is crucial in each instance of organizational change (Oreg, Vakola, and Armenakis, 2011). Because they act as mentors and supporters, ethical leaders can also influence their teams by lowering ambiguity and boosting their willingness to adapt.
- *To Create Win-Win Outcomes:* For both employees and organizations, ethical leadership makes use of their position of power and influence. Employees are coached by ethical leaders to develop a level of personal and professional competence that allows them to succeed while being more tenacious and consistent. A leader's ethical behavior has an indirect impact on the norms that permeate the entire company, which has an impact on the workers. Ethical leaders accept accountability for both successful and unsuccessful results. Employees who work under ethical leadership are more likely to notice and absorb the values and behaviors conveyed by that leadership and make greater efforts to make their own behavior more ethical, according to research by Zhu, Trevino, and Zheng (2016).
- *Loyal Employees:* By encouraging, fostering, and creating a culture of trust and respect, ethical leaders create the ideal environment for employees. Significant advantages emerge from this, such as reduced turnover, increased output, and increased loyalty. Once they experience and see honest leadership, workers will feel

they have made a wise choice to join the company. Team members have fewer reasons to look elsewhere when leaders act justly and fairly (Long, 2020).

A strong emphasis on morals and ethics creates a positive work environment that fosters employee understanding and an improved mood, which boosts morale (Smith and Ellsworth, 1985). Each team member will want to try and contribute to furthering the organization's mission when they are aware that it is acting morally and for the benefit of the larger good (Bonett, 1992), which will increase motivation. Organizations with moral leaders are less likely to experience sudden crises due to internal variables, making them more stable (Mwita, 2000). External parties like donors and partners frequently recognize and value this (Mwita, 2000). Organizations with executives who uphold ethical standards serve as positive role models for others (Mwita, 2000).

✓ *Effect of Ethical Leadership on an Organization*

In a variety of ways, ethical leadership offers companies enormous advantages.

✓ *Increased Sense of Belonging*

Everyone's overall wellbeing will rise when personal and corporate ideals are in harmony and ethical standards are upheld. This results in a positive environment that encourages ethical behavior and reinforces it, creating a positive feedback loop where everyone feels comfortable and is ready to offer their best effort.

✓ *Improved Relationships with Customers*

When customers see and experience ethical leadership and cultural principles, they will feel they made the right choice in choosing your business. This will strengthen your position as one of the market's honest competitors and persuade them to keep doing business with you.

✓ *Respect from Society and Communities*

Companies with moral leaders are respected and valued because they set a positive example for others. These are the organizations that people want to work for, conduct commerce with, and model their own businesses after.

✓ *Support in Times of Crises*

The world is changing quickly, and businesses might encounter many difficulties. However, consumers want to see successful businesses run by moral leaders. Having leaders who act morally, kindly, and respectfully can be the key to surviving difficult times.

✓ *Reliable Workers*

Team members have fewer reasons to leave when leaders act justly and fairly. By encouraging, fostering, and promoting a culture of trust and respect, ethical leaders create the ideal environment for their workforce. Significant advantages result from this, including less turnover, increased production, and loyalty.

✓ *A Rise in Morale*

A positive work environment that places a significant emphasis on values and ethics develops greater understanding and a better mood among employees. When the roots are strong, daily stress and strain are like the wind on a strong tree. Most of the time, people can feel the roots and can tell whether they can rely on them and feel secure or whether they need to be on watch.

✓ *The Market is more Stable*

Due to internal considerations, organizations with moral leaders are less likely to experience abrupt crises. Investors typically acknowledge and value this.

✓ *Increased Drive*

Each team member will want to contribute to advancing the company's mission when they are aware that the business operates ethically and for the benefit of all stakeholders.

➤ *Principled Leadership*

The fundamentals of leadership also support the emergence of fresh leadership philosophies. Several writers have discussed a related idea and characterized a leadership based on principles, a leader who is principled, principles-centered, and who is inspired by their principles. Principled leadership was defined by these same theories as being a leader who is a social entrepreneur (Coleman, 1998), a values-based and ethical leader (Gold, Evans, Earley, Halpin, & Collarbone, 2003; Kreber et al., 2007), and one whose principles are the moral art of leadership (Covey, 1990). Being real while adhering to principles (Agote, Aramburu, & Lines, 2015; Avolio & Gardner, 2005; Walumba et al., 2008).

• *The Importance of Ethics and Values*

Principled leadership, which is founded on a set of fundamental principles and values that direct leaders' behaviors and decision-making, is the type of leadership that is most effective. Strong moral values guide the decisions that principled leaders make, not their own biases or inclinations. Principled leaders make sure that their activities are consistent with the objectives and values of their organization by placing their ideals first. A leadership approach known as "principled leadership" places a strong emphasis on moral conduct, openness, responsibility, and accountability. A set of guiding principles and values serve as the basis for this leadership style's decision-making and execution. Respecting others, acting with honesty, and advancing the greater good are all commitments of principled leaders.

• *Importance of Principled Leadership*

Organizations can gain from principled leadership in a number of ways, including greater employee dedication, loyalty, and trust. An atmosphere of trust and respect is fostered by the transparency, honesty, and accountability that principled leaders establish. A successful organization must cultivate open communication, teamwork, and cooperation, all of which depend on trust. Additionally,

since they create a culture based on their dedication to upholding ethical standards and treating staff members with respect, principled leaders are more likely to draw in and keep outstanding talent.

In addition, ethically responsible executives create an ethical framework for their company, which is a collection of values and principles that the company adopts and uses to guide its actions. It offers a framework for moral judgment and behavior that is consistent with the principles and objectives of the company. Decisions that benefit the organization as a whole, rather than simply a small group of people, are more likely to be made by leaders who are dedicated to advancing the common good and operating with integrity. Employee productivity and engagement consequently rise as a result of the belief that their job matters and makes a difference to the organization's success.

➤ *Characteristics of Principled Leaders*

Principled leaders differ from other leaders in that they have a particular set of traits. These qualities consist of:

- *Integrity:* Strong moral convictions drive principled leaders to always behave in accordance with their values. They act and make decisions in a morally upright, ethical, and transparent manner.
- *Vision:* Principled executives have a distinct vision for where and how they wish to drive the organization. They can create plans to accomplish their objectives because they are strategic thinkers.
- *Courage:* In spite of their unpopularity, principled leaders are not hesitant to make difficult judgments. To accomplish their objectives, they are prepared to take chances and make unpopular decisions.
- *Empathy:* The ability to put oneself in their colleagues' shoes and comprehend their needs and worries is a trait of principled leaders. They may establish a welcoming and welcoming workplace that supports diversity and inclusion.
- *Accountability:* Responsible leaders make both themselves and their team members responsible for their choices and actions. They accept accountability for the results of their actions and are open about the decision-making process.

➤ *Developing Principled Leadership in Organizations*

Training, coaching, and mentoring are just a few of the ways that principled leadership can be fostered. Training programs in ethical leadership are a good method to create moral leadership. These programs instruct leaders on how to make moral choices, advance accountability and openness, and cultivate a climate of respect. Coaching and mentoring are two more efficient methods for creating principled leaders. Emerging leaders can receive advice and support from seasoned leaders, which will aid them in creating their own set of guiding principles and values. Peer mentoring

programs can also be formed, enabling leaders to exchange best practices and learn from one another.

Developing genuine leadership in businesses takes a dedicated effort from both management and people. The following steps can be taken to build principled leadership in organizations:

- *Establish a Code of Ethics:* Companies should create an ethics code that describes their beliefs and expectations for employee conduct. All staff members should be informed of this code, and it should be consistently upheld.
- *Lead by Example:* Management ought to set a good example and act with integrity when making decisions and taking actions. This establishes the tone for the entire company and highlights the value of moral leadership.
- *Provide Training:* Employees should receive training from their employers on ethical decision-making and principled leadership. The organization's principles and expectations should be reinforced during this continuing training.
- *Foster a Culture of Transparency:* Organizations should promote an environment where open dialogue and honesty are valued. This encourages staff to report unethical activity when they witness it and works to stop it from happening.
- *Reward Principled Behavior:* Principled conduct, such as honesty and integrity, should be rewarded by organizations through praise and advancement. This highlights the role of moral leadership and motivates staff to act in line with the principles of the company.

In conclusion, ethical leadership is crucial for any organization's success because it lays the groundwork for a climate of sincerity, integrity, and openness. Integrity, vision, courage, empathy, and accountability are essential traits of principled leaders that direct their decisions and actions. The establishment of a code of ethics, setting an example, giving training, building a culture of transparency, and rewarding moral behavior are all necessary for fostering principled leadership in businesses. Organizations may build a culture of trust and moral conduct by putting principled leadership first, which will boost worker engagement, output, and overall performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- A different strategy would be to implement the NDP's recommendations, which were summed up by as stated by Mr. Newham a group of specialists would conduct open, merit-based interviews with a variety of qualified candidates before recommending their top choice to the President for official appointment. When Adv Shamila Batohi was chosen to lead the National Prosecuting Authority, a procedure quite similar to this one was used.

The way judges are chosen by the Judicial Service Commission following a public interview procedure is comparable to this approach as well.

- The research topic that emerged from this research offer a variety of opportunities. The first relates to opportunities for expanding the learning to include ethical leadership for foreign law enforcement and regulatory bodies as an extension of international development, the second to opportunities for expanding the learning to encompass ethical leadership for future research, and the third to opportunities for South African police executive officers.
- Because it has a stigma, integrating ethical leadership into any law enforcement learning inventory is a special challenge. Since ethical behavior is expected of police and law enforcement personnel, attempts to introduce the subject especially at higher levels are frequently not well received. Senior executive officers don't want to be lectured about corruption, said a senior international law enforcement official who attended a subsequent INTERPOL learning event based on this data (Chansue 2017). The distinction between this learning strategy being preventative and developmental rather than remedial the former being an investment and the latter being corrective—stands out in this context.
- A potential area for future research is how top executive officers in law enforcement apply their knowledge of ethical leadership in their workplaces and professional lives. Training could greatly improve awareness of ethical leadership within the multifaceted and multidimensional activities of law enforcement and regulation across many locations.
- The establishment of partner learning opportunities for both entry-level and senior executive level officers is the final area of prospective future research. Law enforcement suffers from a severe lack of strong, driven, moral leadership at all levels. Senior executive officers significantly influence how staff members perceive, interpret, and understand workplace values, claim Mayer et al. (2009). As a result, it is likely a barrier that there isn't an ethics learning story present at the beginning. Entry level officers will have a better chance of instilling morally upright normative behaviors if they can have an appreciation or grasp of what it means to think ethically early in their careers. This is because front-line leaders will be more inclined to frame issues ethically. Similar to this, the value of the investment in the intermediate strata is negated by the lack of a comparable learning opportunity for senior executive executives. There is no situation that would be more upsetting for a front-line supervisor who has developed their ethical voice than to engage in discussion with a senior officer who has not yet mastered the vocabulary of "ethical leadership." If hubris is a contributing element to the current state of affairs, it is possible that hubris at the highest levels poses the greatest threat to the provision of moral leadership in law enforcement for our communities.

III. CONCLUSION

It would be naive to believe that the choice of the police chief can be fully separated from political and historical factors since it will always be a very delicate topic. Likewise, it will be a while before a candidate's alleged allegiances to a particular party are disregarded. However, it is best to at least downplay these two fundamentally unimportant factors, and above all, the appointment should not be influenced by factionalism within the ruling party. Obviously, saying than doing.

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